

FREE VIBRATION OF THERMALLY LOADED LAMINATED COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The free vibrational characteristics of laminated composite under the influence of thermal load have been studied in this work. The laminate is assumed to be subjected to uniform temperature through the thickness and the analysis has been carried out using finite element method. Both symmetric and antisymmetric (angle-ply and cross-ply) laminates with simply support and clamped edge conditions are considered. It has been found that the nature of variation of square of frequency of vibration with the temperature is linear/piecewise linear in the case of simply supported laminates. For clamped edge conditions the variation is found to be nonlinear. The laminate in which inplane normal displacement is not constrained, has higher critical temperature for buckling than the case in which the inplane normal displacement is constrained. Also the effect of material properties has been studied.

Keywords: Laminated composite, angle-ply, cross-ply, free vibration, thermal load, thermal buckling, critical temperature, mode shape.

1. INTRODUCTION

The effect of temperature on the structural behaviour plays an important role in the analysis and design of structural components. Thin walled structural elements, particularly those used in aircraft structures, nuclear reactor vessels etc. are vulnerable to thermal loadings. There are many practical situations in which the structural components undergo vibration in the presence of initial stress developed due to external loads or thermal loads. If the nature of stress developed is compression, the frequency of vibration decreases and in the limit it becomes zero and the load corresponding to this is the buckling load. It has been established [1,2,3,4] that when two opposite edges of an isotropic plate are simply supported and subjected to uniform compression and the other edges under any type of support conditions, the square of frequency varies linearly with the inplane load. Under any

other combination of boundary conditions and loadings this linear relationship has not been established clearly. As seen from literature [5], the same behaviour has been reported in the case of laminated composite also. If the laminate is subjected to thermal loads the state of stress developed will be biaxial in nature and normal load ratio will be very much different from unity depending upon the coefficients of thermal expansion in the principal material directions. Also unlike the mechanical loading, the load ratio changes as the fibre orientation angle varies. A comprehensive review on the effects of thermal loads on the structural behaviour like, flexure, buckling and vibration of plates has been reported in the literature [6]. This includes few works [7,8] dealing with the dynamic response of the laminated composite subjected to thermal shock. The present work deals with the analysis of free vibration behaviour of laminated composites under thermal load due to uniform temperature through the thickness. The parameters considered for the study includes (1) lamination sequence (2) aspect ratio of the plate (3) support conditions and (4) material properties.

2. METHOD OF SOLUTION

In the present work the well known and versatile [9] nine noded Lagrangian plate element based on Mindlin plate theory with u, v, w, θ_x and θ_y as degrees of freedom at its nodes, has been used. Making use of the formulation and definition [9] for the structural stiffness, geometric stiffness and mass matrices the governing equations for the present problem can be written as

$$([K_s] + [K_g] - \omega^2 [M]) \{q\} = 0 \quad (1)$$

The method of solution is as follows. First, thermal stress analysis of the laminate is carried out to fix the state of stress for a specified temperature making use of the equation

$$[K_s] \{q\} = \{F\} \quad (2)$$

where $\{F\}$ is the equivalent nodal force vector due to the thermal loads [10]. Using the state of stress geometric stiffness matrix is defined and the eigen analysis is carried out using

$$([K_s] + \lambda [K_g]) \{q\} = 0 \quad (3)$$

in which λ is the eigen value which multiplies the specified temperature to get the critical temperature for buckling (T_{cr}). Then for fractional values of T_{cr} , using Equation (1) eigen analysis is carried out to find the variation of frequency with the temperature.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The program developed to form the structural stiffness, geometric stiffness and mass matrices and extract the eigen values has been verified against the exact values as shown in Table 1. The values within bracket represent the reference values and the subscript indicates the reference number. The results have been obtained using a mesh size of 6×6 (full plate) and the values are in good agreement with the exact values. Hence the same discretisation has been used in the present study. The boundary conditions used in the analysis are as follows [15]. Simple support - S1 : $w = 0, M_n = 0, u_n = 0, u_t = 0$; S2 : $w = 0, M_n = 0, N_n = 0, u_t = 0$; S3 : $w = 0, M_n = 0, u_n = 0, N_{nt} = 0$. Clamped - C1 : $w = 0, w_{,n} = 0, u_n = 0, u_t = 0$; C2 : $w = 0, w_{,n} = 0, N_n = 0, u_t = 0$; C3 : $w = 0, w_{,n} = 0, u_n = 0, N_{nt} = 0$.

Table 1

Support Conditions	Buckling coefficient			Frequency Parameter	
	Mechanical (uniaxial) $k = N_x b^2/\pi^2 D$	Thermal $\tau = \alpha T_{cr} a^2/h^2$		Isotropic $\lambda = \omega^2 b^4 \rho h/D$	Laminate $\lambda = \omega^2 b^4 \rho/E_T h^2$
		Isotropic	Orthotropic		
Simply support	3.996 (4.0) ₁₁	1.264 (1.265) ₁₂	9.43 (9.45) ₁₃	19.72 (19.74) ₁₄	73.36 (74.41) ₅
Clamped	10.062 (10.07) ₁₁	338.40 (337.420) ₁₂	34.19 (33.78) ₁₃	35.93 (39.99) ₁₄	-

3.1 Angle-ply laminate

The variations of frequency parameter (Ω) with the thermal loading coefficient (τ) for θ square symmetric (solid line) and antisymmetric (dash line) laminates are shown in Figure 1. Both the laminates exhibits fully linear relationship for the fibre orientation angles ($\theta = 0^\circ, 30^\circ$ and 45°) considered. Also it is found that (since $\alpha = 1$) the nature of variations is identical for the complement angles ($0^\circ, 90^\circ$ and $30^\circ, 60^\circ$). In the case of symmetric laminate the nature of variations under S1 and S3 support conditions are same. The fundamental frequency and critical temperature increase as θ increases and are maximum at 45° . For antisymmetric laminate there is considerable difference between S1 and S3 conditions with the values of S1 being higher than that for S3. This has happened inspite of the fact that the thermal stress distributions are same under both conditions. Possible explanation for this observation is as follows. An antisymmetric laminate possesses bending-shear coupling (B_{16} and B_{26}). Hence when the laminate under goes flexural vibration the coupling coefficients induce tangential displacements which are prevented at the edges in S1 case and allowed in S3. Hence the laminate under S3 conditions is flexible compared to that under S1 conditions. Also for both support conditions 30° laminate gives raise to lowest fundamental frequency and T_{cr} . The reason for this is that the coupling coefficients B_{16} and B_{26} are maximum for 30° . Figure 2 shows the variation of frequency

FIG 1 FREQUENCY PARAMETER VS. THERMAL LOADING COEFFICIENT FOR SYMMETRIC AND ANTISYMMETRIC ANGLE PLY LAMINATES

FIG 2 FREQUENCY PARAMETER VS THERMAL LOADING COEFFICIENT FOR SYMMETRIC AND ANTISYMMETRIC ANGLE PLY LAMINATES UNDER S3 CONDITIONS

parameter with the thermal loading coefficient for a square symmetric and antisymmetric laminates under S2 support conditions. Compared to S1 and S3 conditions the T_{cr} values are higher for S2 conditions for both the type of laminates. As the inplane displacement component normal to laminate edge is not constrained the intensity of thermal stress developed is relatively lower than that for S1 or S3 and hence higher T_{cr} values for S2 conditions. The T_{cr} values for symmetric and antisymmetric laminates are same; whereas the fundamental frequency values are different for $\theta = 30^\circ$ and 45° . In contrast for S1 and S3 conditions T_{cr} value is minimum for $\theta = 45^\circ$ and maximum for $\theta = 0^\circ$ or 90° . For $\theta = 0^\circ$ and 90° the nature of variations are one and the same for both the laminates, as they represent a case of simple orthotropic plate. The nature of variation is fully linear for $\theta = 30^\circ$ and 45° and piecewise linear for $\theta = 0^\circ$ and 90° with two segments.

FIG. 3 FREQUENCY PARAMETER VS THERMAL LOADING COEFFICIENT FOR SYMMETRIC AND ANTI-SYMMETRIC LAMINATES

FIG. 4 FREQUENCY PARAMETER VS THERMAL LOADING COEFFICIENT FOR SYMMETRIC AND ANTI-SYMMETRIC LAMINATES UNDER C2 SUPPORT CONDITIONS

The temperature effects on the frequency of vibration of a square symmetric and antisymmetric laminate under C1 and C3 conditions are shown in Figure 3. The nature of variations are found to be same for both the support conditions. For all fibre orientation angles considered the mode shapes of fundamental vibration and critical buckling are one and same ($m = n = 1$) and the nature of variation is found to be nonlinear. The thin line drawn shows the possible linear relationship and with respect to that the deviation from linearly can be seen. The extent of nonlinearity is more for symmetric laminate than the antisymmetric one. Also in contrast to the simply supported case (Figure 1) the T_{cr} and fundamental frequency values decrease as θ increases reaching minimum at $\theta = 45^\circ$. The nature of variation of frequency under C2 support conditions is shown in Figure 4. The nature of variation is found to be nonlinear for both the type of laminates and the fundamental frequency and T_{cr} values are higher than that for C1 or C3 conditions. For $\theta = 0^\circ$ the mode shapes to buckling ($m = 1, n = 3$) and the fundamental frequency ($m = n = 1$) are different. For $\theta = 30^\circ$ and 45° the mode shapes are same ($m = n = 1$).

3.2 Cross-ply laminate

The effects of thermal loading on the free vibrational characteristics for a square symmetric and antisymmetric laminates under S1, S2 and S3 conditions are shown in Figure 5. The nature of variation is found to be fully linear for all cases considered. As observed

in the case of anglo-ply laminate here also the T_{cr} values are higher for S2 conditions compared to S1 or S3. The variations of frequency parameter with the thermal loading coefficient for a rectangular ($\alpha = 2$) symmetric and antisymmetric laminates under S1, S2 and S3 conditions are shown in Figure 6. The nature of variation is found to be fully linear for all cases considered. This is in contrast to the rectangular ($\alpha = 2$) isotropic plate, subjected to uniaxial compression, in which the nature of variation is piecewise linear with the number of segments equal to the aspect ratio. In the case of laminated plate subjected to thermal load, the stress developed will be biaxial in nature and hence there is a possibility for fully linear relationship. Unlike the square laminate (Figure 5) here the fundamental frequency and T_{cr} values are lower for symmetric laminate ($0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ$) than that for the antisymmetric laminate ($0^\circ/90^\circ$). This is against the expected one since, generally, symmetric laminates are stiffer than the antisymmetric one. If the symmetric lamination sequence is changed to $90^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ$ then the T_{cr} and fundamental frequency values may be higher than that for antisymmetric laminate.

Figure 7 shows the variations of fundamental frequency parameter with thermal loading coefficient for square symmetric and antisymmetric laminates under C1, C2 and C3 conditions. The nature of variation is found to nonlinear. The mode shapes of buckling ($m = 1, n = 3$) and fundamental frequency ($m = n = 1$) are different for symmetric laminate under C2 conditions. For all other cases the mode shapes of buckling and fundamental frequency are same ($m = n = 1$) and deviation from linearity is very small. The nature of variation of frequency parameter for $\alpha = 2$ for both symmetric and antisymmetric laminates are shown in Figure 8. The behaviour of the laminate is similar to that under simply support conditions (Figure 6) except that the nature of variation is nonlinear. Also for antisymmetric laminate under C2 conditions the mode shape of buckling ($m = 3, n = 1$) is different from that for the fundamental frequency ($m = n = 1$). For all other cases, the mode shapes of buckling and fundamental frequency are same ($m = n = 1$) and the deviation from linearity is very small.

FIG. 7 FREQUENCY PARAMETER ν THERMAL LOADING COEFFICIENT FOR SYMMETRIC AND ANTISYMMETRIC CROSS-PLY LAMINATES
 ——— $0^\circ/180^\circ$; - - - $0^\circ/90^\circ$

FIG. 8 FREQUENCY PARAMETER ν THERMAL LOADING COEFFICIENT FOR SYMMETRIC AND ANTISYMMETRIC CROSS-PLY LAMINATES
 ——— $0^\circ/180^\circ$; - - - $0^\circ/90^\circ$

3.3 Effect of material properties

The effect of material properties on the free vibrational characteristics of composite laminate subjected thermal loading are shown Figures 9 and 10. The three sets of material properties considered are $E_L/E_T = 20$, $\alpha_T/\alpha_L = 60$ (Set A); $E_L/E_T = 40$, $\alpha_T/\alpha_L = 40$ (Set B); $E_L/E_T = 60$, $\alpha_T/\alpha_L = 10$ (Set C). $G_{LT}/E_T = 0.5$ and $\nu_{LT} = 0.25$ (for all sets).

FIG. 9 FREQUENCY PARAMETER ν THERMAL LOADING COEFFICIENT FOR ANGLE-PLY AND CROSS PLY LAMINATES
 ——— ANGLE-PLY - - - - - CROSS PLY

FIG. 10 FREQUENCY PARAMETER ν THERMAL LOADING COEFFICIENT FOR SYMMETRIC AND ANTISYMMETRIC ANGLE-PLY LAMINATES
 ○ SYMMETRIC - - - - - ANTISYMMETRIC

Figure 9 shows the variation of frequency parameter with the thermal loading coefficient for the above mentioned set of properties, for a square symmetric and antisymmetric (cross-ply and angle-ply) laminates under S1 support conditions. The nature of variation is found to be linear for all cases considered. Also it is seen that the T_{Cr} and fundamental frequency values increase with the moduli ratio. Figure 10 shows the variation of frequency parameter for a square symmetric and antisymmetric angle-ply laminate

($\theta = 45^\circ$) under C1 support conditions. As observed earlier, the nature of variation is found to be nonlinear for all the cases considered. The mode shapes of critical buckling and fundamental frequency are same for both the types of laminate. Here again it is seen that the T_{cr} values increase with the moduli ratio. It is seen that deviation from linearity is more for symmetric laminate than the antisymmetric laminate.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The free vibrational characteristics of composite laminate under the influence of thermal loads have been studied using finite element method and the following observations have been made. (1) The nature of variation of square of frequency with the temperature is found to be linear (fully or piecewise) for simply support conditions. (2) The nature of variation is nonlinear for clamped edge conditions. (3) T_{cr} values are higher for support conditions in which inplane normal displacement components are not constrained (S2 or C2) than those in which the normal displacement components are constrained (S1, S3 or C1, C3). (4) The effects of material properties have also been studied and T_{cr} values are found to increase as moduli ratio increases.

LIST OF SYMBOLS

a	- Plate length	t	- Tangential direction
b	- Plate width	T	- Transverse direction
B_{ij}	- Coupling co-efficients	T_{cr}	- Critical temperature
D	- Flexural rigidity	u	- Inplane disp. component
E_L	- Young's modulus along L	u	- Displacement along x-direction
E_T	- Young's modulus along T	v	- Displacement along y-direction
{F}	- Nodal load vector	w	- Displacement along z-direction
h	- Laminate thickness	α	- Aspect ratio (a/b)
$[K_s]$	- Structure stiffness matrix	α_L	- Coeff. of linear expn. along L
$[K_g]$	- Structure geometric stiff matrix	α_T	- Coeff. of linear expn. along T
$[M]$	- Structure mass matrix	θ_x	- Rotation in xz plane
L	- Fibre direction	θ_y	- Rotation in yz plane
M	- Moment resultants	ω	- Angular frequency
N	- Stress resultants	ρ	- Density of material
n	- Normal direction	Ω	- Freq. parameter, $\omega^2 \rho b^4 / E_T h^2$
{q}	- Nodal displacement vector	τ	- Therm. load. coeff. $\alpha_L T_{cr} a^2 / h^2$

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